

EDEN ISS

D 7.7 - Lecture Material

prepared for

WP 7.1 - Public Engagement

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Executive summary

EDEN ISS engaged the next generation of space explorers through an educational outreach program that offered to teachers and pupils information and activities related to the cultivation of plants for the purpose of growing food in space, either on the International Space Station or further destinations like the Moon and Mars. The techniques and technologies for food production in space can also be utilised for terrestrial applications.

The report describes the components of the lecture material consisting of a presentation on the EDEN ISS project and a manual for growing salad without soil. All information is publicly accessible through the EDEN ISS website.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
AIAA	American Institute of Aeronautics	IP	Intellectual Property
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
AST	Airbus Defence and Space	ISS	International Space Station
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	ISLWG	Information Systems Liaison Working Group
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
CEA	Controlled Environment Agriculture	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
CNR	National Research Council	LSG	LIQUIFER Systems Group
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research	M#	Month Number
D	Deliverable	PP	Program Participants
DLO	Wageningen University and Research	RD	Reference Document
DLR	German Aerospace Center	R&D	Research & Development
DLR-RY	German Aerospace Center - Institute of Space Systems	SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
EC	European Commission	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
EDEN	Evolution and Design of Environmentally-Closed Nutrition-Sources	TBD	To Be Determined
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
ESA	European Space Agency	UoG	University of Guelph
EU	European Union	WP	Work Package
HS	Heliospectra AB		
IAC	International Astronautical Congress		

1 Introduction

1.1 *Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS Project*

The EDEN ISS project is interested in promoting its progress in space greenhouse research to the scientific community and to the general public as to ensure continuation of project objectives. The (ultimate) goal of the EDEN ISS project is to further advance Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA) technologies for safe food production on-board the International Space Station (ISS) and other planetary outposts.

The EDEN ISS consortium is interested in, and committed to, creating awareness and excitement regarding the future of human space exploration, through the open access distribution of project documents and results to researchers and a proactive educational school program designed for students within the EU and Canada.

A critical component of future, human space exploration will be the supply of edible food. The development of innovations associated with cultivating food in closed-loop systems is an integral part of a sustainable human presence in space. EDEN ISS will develop an advanced nutrient delivery system, a high-performance LED lighting system, a bio-detection and decontamination system and food quality and safety procedures and technologies.

Distribution of the project results to interested parties guarantees an impact to the European economy and enhances the spin-off potential of these validated technologies.

Furthermore, EDEN ISS will study the utilization of the constructed facility for future system implementations (i.e., for other environments/applications).

1.2 *Purpose and scope of this document*

This document presents an overview of the lecture material which was produced for classroom activities related to the EDEN ISS project. The lecture material was prepared for teachers and also anyone else who wanted to get an insight into the project.

2 Lecture Material overview

Lecture material for schools (age range between 6 and 12 years) and universities was made available on 30.11.2018, and has been shared on the project website under “Education” for teachers and/or professors worldwide. It offers information and suggests activities in the topics of space, biology, and growing food under specific environmental conditions appropriate to learning abilities.

Download lecture material

https://eden-iss.net/wp-content/uploads/EDENISSProject_Description_final_red.pptx

[DOWNLOAD directions on How to grow your seeds without the use of soil in English](#)

https://eden-iss.net/wp-content/uploads/bottlecapdirections_final.pdf

The lecture material is connected to the Antarctic seed campaign and to the Children’s Seed Campaign Competition which ran from November 30th, 2018 to February 3rd, 2019. The seeds were taken by DLR personnel to the Neumayer III station and were brought back to Europe after they had stayed in Antarctica for a number of weeks. The seeds are available to classrooms in Europe and Canada. These were also part of the Experiment Toolkit which was sent to students upon request.

The Experiment Toolkit is a plant growth experiment for school children and pupils. The kits have been developed by DLR and highlight the key issues of CEA technologies and different growth procedures related to cultivating plants in space. The pupils could learn different aspects about Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems (BLSS) and the role of higher plants in human space exploration endeavours. Seeds from the Antarctic seed campaign are included in the Experiment toolkit.

Figure 2-1: Snapshot of Education Section on EDEN ISS website

3 Lecture Material

This chapter displays the PowerPoint slides for the teachers, showing images accompanied by explanations provided in the notes of the PowerPoint presentation.

Figure 3-1: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 1 including notes

Sustained human presence in space requires the development of new technologies to maintain environmental control, manage waste, provide water, oxygen and food, and to keep astronauts healthy and psychologically fit.

EDEN ISS uses Controlled-Environment Agriculture technologies to grow plants in extreme conditions

With lessons learned from this research project, new facilities can be developed for use in space, on the Moon or on Mars.

Figure 3-2: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 2 including notes

EDEN ISS is a four-year project

Funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

14 international partners lend their expertise in the development of the project.

Figure 3-3: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 3 including notes

- Project EDEN ISS focuses on cultivating plants in controlled environments.
- New technologies are developed to provide plants with all the essential requirements they need to grow including:
 - A nutrient delivery system
 - High-performance LED lighting system
 - Imaging systems for monitoring plant health

The plants that are grown at EDEN ISS do not require normative growing practices.

Soil nor Sunlight are required, and water usage is significantly reduced.

All technological processes are carefully monitored to ensure plant health and safety and special programs are designed to maximize plant growth and vitality.

Figure 3-4: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 4 including notes

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

mobile container

EDEN's concept uses standardized shipping containers, fitted with food cultivation technologies for the purpose of growing plants in a controlled environment – anywhere.

Figure 3-5: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 5 including notes

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

[1] Future Exploration Greenhouse

Comprised of three sections

Standardized shipping containers are used for easy mobility purposes

Two such containers are used in the EDEN ISS project, and three distinct zones are created for performing the specific tasks related to controlled environment plant cultivation.

The **Future Exploration Greenhouse** is the main plant growth area of the facility

Figure 3-6: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 6 including notes

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

Figure 3-7: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 7 including notes

The **Service Section** houses:

- the main support subsystems, including, thermal, power, air management and nutrient/water subsystems
- a working space for pre- and post- harvesting procedures

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

Figure 3-8: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 8 including notes

The **cold porch / airlock** is a small buffer room to limit the entry of cold air into the greenhouse

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

Figure 3-9: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 9 including notes

The mobile container is fitted with food cultivation technologies including:

A Plant cultivation rack – a structural system that supports growth trays

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

Figure 3-10: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 10 including notes

The high-performance **LED lighting system** offers different wavelengths of light in blue, red, red+blue (pink) and white

Different plants prefer different light spectra to grow most efficiently – the EDEN ISS team works to identify the best lighting parameters for each plant that is grown in the facility

Figure 3-11: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 11 including notes

The **Atmosphere management and thermal control** subsystem is used to maintain the correct temperature, humidity, and flow rate throughout the facility, in particular in the greenhouse

Carbon dioxide and oxygen levels are also monitored and controlled for optimal growing conditions.

Figure 3-12: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 12 including notes

The **Nutrient delivery system:**

- controls the mixing of the water and nutrient solutions that are used to feed the plants
- delivers the solution to the roots of the plants

Figure 3-13: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 13 including notes

The **work area** houses all the control systems used by the different subsystems

The environmental conditions that exist in the greenhouse are monitored and controlled from the work area

Figure 3-14: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 14 including notes

The **ISPR cultivation rack** is a separate experiment running within the facility and looks at plant growth inside a single enclosed compartment. It is a testbed for future use on the International Space Station

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

Inside the Future Exploration Greenhouse a variety of plants are grown using controlled environmental parameters, allowing optimal growth without the use of sunlight or soil, and reducing the amount of water needed for plant cultivation.

Figure 3-15: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 15 including notes

EDEN ISS concept
mobile container + food cultivation technologies = ability to grow plants in a controlled environment - anywhere

The EDEN ISS system can be transported and used to sustain human life in various applications and contexts

Pictured: EDEN ISS in Antarctica

An essential part of the EDEN ISS project is the testing of the facility in extreme environmental conditions.

Antarctica was chosen as a test site because it is one of the harshest environments on earth

Learning how the facility and all of its sub-systems operate in Antarctica – provides an excellent basis for designing similar facilities for use off of Earth, including on the Moon or on Mars.

Figure 3-16: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 16 including notes

EDEN ISS Mission setup
Transport of EDEN ISS - Bremen, Germany to Antarctica

The facility was initially set-up at the DLR campus in Bremen, Germany.

It was transported to Antarctica, via South Africa

Figure 3-17: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 17 including notes

Transport of EDEN ISS

Images show the arrival of EDEN ISS containers in Antarctica via transport ship AGULHAS II

The containers were unloaded and transferred to the mission site 25 kilometres away via Pisten-Bullys

The Mobile Test Facility was placed on a structural platform, 400m away from the Neumayer Station III.

Neumayer Station III is a German Antarctic research center, operated by the Alfred-Wegener-Institute.

Figure 3-18: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 18 including notes

EDEN ISS setup in Antarctica – hardware and seed trays

Images show the EDEN ISS team preparing the mobile container for its mission:

- Internal and external hardware is installed and all subsystems are made operational
- Seedlings are prepared in seed trays

Paul Zabel from DLR is the leading scientist of the EDEN ISS mission and is responsible for conducting all the plant experiments within the facility during its one-year test period.

During the mission, Paul lives as part of the 10-person crew of the Neumayer Station III and the vegetables that are produced within the facility are used to supplement the diets of crew members.

Figure 3-19: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 19 including notes

EDEN ISS MISSION OPERATION - Antarctica

The operations phase of the mission started in March 2018

Paul Zabel handles on-site operations and performs routine activities such as seeding, monitoring subsystems and harvesting.

Figure 3-20: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 20 including notes

EDEN ISS Greenhouse to salad plate

Greenhouse cultivation of edible vegetables is successful and supplements the diet of crew members aboard the Neumayer Station.

On average, the following amounts of each vegetable are produced each week, measured in kilograms:

- Cucumber 1.46
- Lettuce 0.98
- Leafy greens 1.00
- Tomato 0.77
- Kohlrabi 0.34
- Herbs 0.25
- Radish 0.14

Figure 3-21: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 21 including notes

EDEN ISS growing principle - HYDROPONICS

Generally, plants require soil from which they receive water, minerals and stability.

On a space station, plants are not exposed to wind or other weather conditions, therefore the stability and anchoring factor can be omitted in plant cultivation in space.

Water and minerals, on the other hand, are absolutely necessary requirements.

Since these can be absorbed directly from the roots of the plant, a mineral-enriched water vapour can replace the need for soil.

This technique of plant cultivation is called hydroponics, or aeroponics.

The Nutrient Delivery system of the EDEN ISS facility delivers a mineral-enriched solution directly to the exposed roots of the plants that are grown.

Figure 3-22: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 22 including notes

EDEN ISS monitoring plant health

Along with more traditional methods of measuring plant vitality, advanced systems for measuring plant health through imaging processes are developed in the EDEN ISS project.

Cameras collect daily images for each of the growth trays in the greenhouse.

The images that are captured are transferred as data files to DLR in Bremen and to the NASA Life Sciences Data Archive for evaluation.

Software programs have been developed to:

- track the growth rate of crops
- Monitor plant health
- Identify problematic growth conditions

Figure 3-23: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 23 including notes

In addition, plant health is monitored using different laboratory analysis methods to detect if there is any microbiological contamination of the plants

Microbial contamination can develop differently under varying conditions, dependent on, among others, temperature, growth media, oxygen levels and pH-values.

Figure 3-24: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 24 including notes

Animation of the EDEN ISS Greenhouse

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fix7jrdfaHE&t=118s>

EDEN ISS Summary video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fix7jrdfaHE&t=118s>

Figure 3-25: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 25 including notes

Thank you for learning about the EDEN ISS project and Controlled Environment Agriculture technologies for growing plants on Earth and in space.

-From the EDEN ISS team

Figure 3-26: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 26 including notes

The end

Figure 3-27: EDEN ISS Lecture Material slide 27 including notes

4 Bottle crop

For the classroom focus of EDEN ISS, teachers could order Antarctic Seeds. Along with the lecture material, the manual to grow salad in simple plastic bottle using hydroponics as growth technique was provided so that with the seeds “Antarctic” salad like the one grown in Antarctica could be cultivated and harvested.

The following Figures display the manual.

EDEN ISS Bottle Salad

Description of Hydroponic Plant Growth
& Directions for growing your very own hydroponic salad greens

Did you know that plants can grow in the air if its roots are kept moist with nutrient-enriched water?

- Generally, plants require soil from which they receive water, minerals and stability
- On a space station, plants are not exposed to wind or other weather conditions, therefore the stability and anchoring factor can be omitted in plant cultivation in space
- Water and minerals, on the other hand, are absolutely necessary requirements
- Since water and minerals can be absorbed directly from the roots of the plant, a mineral-enriched water vapor can replace the need for soil

This technique of plant cultivation is called **hydroponics or aeroponics**

EDEN ISS Bottle Salad

This tutorial explains how to build a self-watering plant pot without the use of any soil

What you need

- Plastic bottle with lid
- Scissors
- Gimlet tool
- Coffee filter or cotton pad
- Seeds
- Aluminium foil
- Water
- Possibly plant food (fertilizer)

Figure 4-1: EDEN ISS bottle crop manual page 1

EDEN ISS Bottle Salad
 How to make it in six easy steps

- Cut the plastic bottle in half

- Drill small holes in the bottle cap

- Put a thin piece of coffee filter or cotton into the lid
- Fill the lower half of the bottle with water

- Insert the upper half of the bottle upside down into the lower half

The bottle cap must be slightly submerged in water, so that the coffee filter/cotton wool can soak it up.

Throughout plant growth, the bottle cap should remain in contact with water.

Figure 4-2: EDEN ISS bottle crop manual page 2

EDEN ISS Bottle Salad

How to make it in six easy steps

- Place seeds on the coffee filter / cotton wool

- Wrap the lower half in aluminum foil so that no light can penetrate the root zone

>This prevents algae from forming

TIPS

- Make sure that the bottle cap stays in contact with water throughout the duration of plant growth. You will need to regularly add water into the lower half of the bottle crop
- You may add plant fertilizer to the water

If you plant herbs or lettuce, it will be ready to be harvested and eaten in a few weeks

ENJOY!

Figure 4-3: EDEN ISS bottle crop manual page 3

5 Summary

The report documents the material which has been produced to support teachers with their educational activities and to provide them sufficient information so that they can speak to the young pupils and students about the EDEN ISS project. Supplementary to the information in the PowerPoint presentation are all open access articles about the project and the website including YouTube videos and animations.

In addition, the lecture material was complemented with a DIY experiment, the Bottle Crop, and seeds which had been flown to Antarctica.

The overall goal was to educate, inspire and enlighten the young people and students about the possibilities of growing food in space and experiment with the soilless techniques of aero- and hydroponics. Achieving this goal will ultimately not only pave the way for sustainable food growth on Earth but also expand possibilities of human exploration beyond Earth orbit.